

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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**“BOOKMATY PRINT”
TOSHKENT – 2025**

UO‘K: 811(075)

KBK: 81.1

T 42

Tilshunoslikning amaliy masalalari: zamonaviy tilshunoslikning dolzarb muammolari, yechimlari, taraqqiyoti va istiqbollari [Matn]: to‘plam. – Toshkent: Bookmany print, 2025. – 654 b.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 20-oktabrdagi “Mamlakatimizda o‘zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PF-6084-sonli Farmoniga muvofiq “2020-2030-yillarda o‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi”da belgilangan vazifalarning ijrosini ta’minlash maqsadida hamda Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligining 2024-yil 27-dekabrdagi 490-sonli buyrug‘iga asosan **Guliston davlat universitetida 2025-yil 29-30-sentabr kunlari** o‘tkazilgan **“TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI”** mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. Anjuman zamonaviy tilshunoslikning eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzulari va amaliy masalalariga doir uslubiy ishlanmalarni aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

ISBN 978-9910-06-724-2

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The Variability of the Category of Negation in Linguistics

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Negation expresses the non-existence of something in objective reality. The category of negation can be examined both logically and grammatically. Accordingly, this category is studied within both the field of logic and that of linguistics. While the logical foundation of negation is universal across all languages, the grammatical means by which it is expressed are highly diverse. Logical negation refers to negative judgments, whereas grammatical negation is typically expressed through sentences using a variety of tools. In linguistics, negation is primarily considered in the interaction between content and form—in particular, the relationship between sentence structure and the meaning it conveys.

Laws that exist independently of human will also apply to language. Without understanding these objective patterns, it is impossible to determine the causes and nature of changes in language, the historical patterns of language development, and the factors influencing them. Negation is considered an independent grammatical category. Among grammatical categories, the category of negation attracts particular attention due to the breadth of its scope and the richness of its expression.[2. 14]

This category emerges through comparison with and opposition to affirmation. Negation is one of the main devices that affect sentence structure and participate in constructing the sentence. Therefore, the logical-grammatical analysis of negation is

essential in determining the structure of sentences and judgments. The linguistic manifestations of negation in various languages reveal typological similarities and differences. Through negative words, an entire sentence or a specific part of it can be negated, depending on the situational context. Two types of negation are generally distinguished in linguistics: general and partial negation. In general negation, the negative word applies to the entire sentence content, most often negating the predicate. In partial negation, one word within the sentence is negated, with the negative word placed near the constituent it negates.

The category of negation has been studied since ancient times. Analyzing the category of negation as a functional-semantic category and examining its explicit and implicit expression tools are of significant theoretical and practical importance. The semantics of negation can be realized through expression tools at various linguistic levels—lexical, grammatical, lexical-grammatical, and lexical-syntactic.

Several perspectives exist regarding the logical and linguistic nature of negation. In formal logic, negation is explained under the category of “non-existence.” Ancient philosophers expressed this concept with terms such as “absence” and “non-being.” Although the category of logical negation forms the core of the category of linguistic negation, it does not fully encompass it. Unlike logical negation, linguistic negation fulfills multiple functions, has relative independence, and possesses its own semantic capacity. For example, not all sentences containing a negation marker correspond to a logical negation; they can also express affirmation, prohibition, or questions.

Logical negation exists in all languages and should thus be regarded as a language universal. Its logical content includes meanings of negativity, deprivation, difference, and alternative existence. However, the semantic scope of linguistic negation may also include protest, rejection, prohibition, and so on. Furthermore, the form of negation can carry positive semantic meanings. This may alter individual lexical units or entire syntactic constructions. V.N. Bondarenko sees the difference between logical and grammatical negation in the universality of logical negation and its ability to be expressed through various linguistic means [5. 13].

As a linguistic category, negation has relative independence and contains a semantic volume that, while not equivalent to the logical category, encompasses it. In a strictly syntactic sense, the category of negation can express not only a negative judgment but also specific negation, contrast, exception, subjective questions, prohibition, and emphatic affirmation. [4. 34]

When combined with affirmation, negation reflects two forms of thought: concept and judgment. From this perspective, negation may be seen as a formal universal across all languages. It is a component of thought and its sentence-level expression. Thus, negation can be regarded as a structural-semantic modifier at the syntactic level of lexical meaning and sentence structure. Affirmation exists as the opposite of negation and lacks any formal markers in a sentence; it is expressed through a zero marker and conveyed only through semantics. Negation, as the opposite of affirmation, creates a new variant. If a feature can be affirmed, it can also be negated. Many linguists view negation as a variant of affirmative sentence forms,

a transformation of the positive declarative form. Psycholinguists such as O. Jespersen and H. Sweet associate negation with resistance and aversion in real speech, negation often has greater stylistic and emotional potential than affirmation. [10. 51]

Bondarenko observes that the function of negative sentences is not to transmit new information, but to reject, contradict, or correct the statements of the interlocutor. Special sentence forms are used to express affirmation and negation. Negation plays a particular role in sentence structure. While opposition between affirmative and negative sentences exists in all languages, the ways negation is expressed differ. Affirmative nominal sentences are typically more informative, followed by qualifying, characterizing, or specifying content based on the noun's communicative valency. [5. 33]

In linguistics, affirmative and negative sentences are studied in their mutual relationship. Each negation derives from an affirmation. A negative sentence is constructed similarly to an affirmative one; the only difference is the presence of a negation marker. Every declarative sentence in any language has a correlate, which is the negative sentence. In such sentences, the action or judgment subjectively performed is not confirmed—it does not occur. For instance, Peshkovsky considers negation a syntactic category. He argues that these categories do not express relations between words or word combinations but reflect the speaker's attitude toward their speech and its parts. Thus, these categories are always studied within syntax. [7. 48]

In English and Azerbaijani, two negative elements can cancel each other out, resulting in an affirmative meaning. This occurs only when the two negatives refer to the same object or concept—a feature known in linguistics as double negation. As a result, the meaning of negation is nullified, and the construction conveys affirmation. Using a double negative instead of a direct affirmative form can be considered a stylistic device. S. Abdullayev notes that double negation, depending on the communicative situation and textual context, can either weaken or intensify affirmation. In English, the combination of the particle “not” with adjectives and adverbs that already contain a negative prefix such as un-, im-, in-, il-, dis-, as well as the suffix -less and the prepositional prefix non-, can result in a positive meaning due to double negation. [1. 44] Examples:

It was impossible not to remark it.

You can't undo the past.

He was not restless.

It may not be nonsense.

It made him hilarious, but not disagreeable.

I can't be unhappy, but neither she, nor he ought to be happy.

In such sentences, the combination of not with affixal negation serves either to affirm or to weaken the force of negation, depending on context. These cases express subtle doubt or nuanced affirmation. Words like “without”, as well as inherently negative verbs such as to fail, to deny, to lack, to refuse, when used with other negators, can also produce affirmative meanings.

Examples:

He found that he couldn't refuse himself to the special writers who travelled long distances to see him.

Martin could not fail to appreciate the keen play of their minds.

I don't deny that you have an excellent appearance—but I will say, richer.

Double negation also frequently appears in conditional clauses. When both the main and subordinate clauses are negated in past tense, the resulting meaning is affirmative, although not always reflecting reality.

Examples:

Perhaps you wouldn't admit it if you hadn't been successful.

It was not her fault, if she did not love him. If you did not disparage them, they would not resent it.

Implicit negative markers such as “hardly, scarcely, barely” serve as adverbial expressions of negation and mean “almost not” or “with difficulty.” These function as negators themselves and do not require an additional negative word like no or not.

Examples:

The parlour was very quiet, so that you could hardly believe you were in the midst of a populous city.

She could hardly prevent herself from laughing aloud.

He could scarcely breathe, and his heart was pounding...

In English, negation is mostly formed analytically, and the primary grammatical means of expressing it is through the negative particle “not.” It serves to negate the verb in the sentence and can appear in various semantic variants. “Not” typically follows auxiliary or modal verbs (do, does, did, have, am, is, are, was, were, shall, should, will, would, can, could, may, might, must, ought). Sometimes, not is contracted with auxiliary verbs to form negative morphemes: don't, doesn't, isn't, won't, wouldn't, hadn't, hasn't, etc.

Examples:

Destiny doesn't send us heralds.

The tragedy of old age is not that one is old, but that one is young.

Oh no, I wouldn't do that if I were you.

In some cases, not takes the place of no when used as an intensifier at the beginning of a sentence:

Examples:

Not even an echo answered me.

Not a leaf stirred on the trees...

In English, to denote the non-existence of a person or object, negative pronouns like no one, nothing, nowhere, none are used.

Examples:

No one is satisfied with his fortune.

Nothing can cure the soul but the senses.

Nowhere in the world was life as monotonous as in this hospital annexe.

None of the big companies made him any overtures.

The negative conjunctions neither...nor, not only...but also, and the subordinating conjunction unless are also used to express negation:

Examples:

I neither like him, nor dislike him.

Love cannot go wrong unless it be a weakling that faints and stumbles by the way.

The negative adverb “never” is another significant means of expressing negation in English. It should not be confused with the adverb of time never, though they are homonymous. As a negative intensifier, it often translates into Azerbaijani as *heç*, *heç bir dəfə də*. As an adverb of time, it means *heç vaxt*.

Examples:

He could never have been so inhuman as to leave her to her fate. – (negative adverb of time)

He never met her eyes and he never smiled. – (negative particle)

I am proud enough never to permit myself to love a man who doesn't love me.

Marriage had never entered his mind as a possibility.

In such sentences, never transforms an affirmative predicate into a negative one.

Unlike Azerbaijani equivalents like *heç vaxt*, which do not inherently negate, never serves as a full negation. Etymologically, never is formed by combining the negative no with the adverb ever. Hence, if never is used in a sentence, the adverb ever cannot be used. Examples of rhetorical inversion with “never”:

But never had he attempted to frame lofty thoughts in words.

Never had he seen such a woman.

Never, in all the women he had heard speak, had he heard a voice like hers.

The word “neither” acts as a negative pronoun, adverb, or conjunction. It denotes the negation of two options simultaneously and is often paired with nor. As a conjunction, neither...nor negates two subjects, attributes, or actions.

Examples:

But you keep telling me I can't. Neither can you.

Neither of us spoke.

Neither of his friends dared to say anything to him.

In English, adverbial negators such as by no means, in no way, not at all also play a major role. These not only negate but also intensify the emotive or emphatic nature of the sentence.

Examples:

She is by no means an inexperienced teacher. We haven't won yet, not by any means.

Other negative pronouns include:

No one, nobody – refer to absence of people. (*heç kim*, *heç kəs*)

No one is satisfied with his fortune.

I know no one who cares...

Nothing – refers to absence of things. (*heç nə*)

Nothing can cure the soul but the senses.

Nowhere – indicates absence of place. (*heç yerdə*)

Nowhere in the world was life as monotonous...

None – used in place of no as a pronoun, often translated as heç biri. It can refer to both countable and uncountable nouns and is used for animate and inanimate entities. None of the big companies made him any overtures. Lester had lost none of his charm for her. Negative conjunctions and structures like neither...nor, not only...but also, and conditional negators like unless are also common:

Examples:

I neither like him nor dislike him.

He was neither loud-voiced nor angry-mannered...

Love cannot go wrong unless it be a weakling that faints and stumbles by the way.

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